

Archiving, sharing and discussing research data on Eastern Europe, South Caucasus and Central Asia

Data Review

Data Citation

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Abstract

The World Values Survey (WVS) is an international research program studying social, political, economic, religious and cultural values of people around the world and contributes to the monitoring of the Sustainable Development Goals using a representative comparative social study - conducted globally every five years - as its main research instrument. The WVS grew out of the European Values Study and was started in 1981 by Professor Ronald Inglehart from the University of Michigan and his team. The WVS currently covers the time period from 1981 to 2022 in more than 120 world societies via 7 separate survey waves. Wave 8 of the survey is being planned which will cover the time frame from 2024-2026. The goal of the Survey is to “assess which impact values stability or change over time has on the social, political and economic development of countries and societies”. The following countries covered by Discuss Data are included in the WVS (in alphabetical order): Armenia in 1997, 2011, 2021 Belarus in 1990, 1996, 2011 Estonia in 1996, 2011 Georgia in 1996, 2009, 2014 Kazakhstan in 2011, 2018 Kyrgyzstan in 2003, 2011, 2020 Latvia in 1996 Lithuania in 1997 Moldova in 1996, 2002, 2006 Russia in 1990, 1995, 2011, 2017 Tajikistan in 2020 Ukraine in 1996, 2006, 2011, 2020 Uzbekistan in 2011, 2022 This data review includes a link to the official World Values Survey website from which both the dataset, as well as all information listed here, is available. In the section “Data and Documentation / Data Download” the questionnaire and a documentation are available for direct download. The documentation includes the codebook and descriptive statistics of the results for all countries. The documentation for the 7th wave of the survey has a total length of 1380 pages. The “statistical data files” containing the original raw data in different formats (csv, R, SAS, SPSS and STATA) are available for download immediately after submission of the online registration form.

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Data Review - World Values Survey

The World Values Survey (WVS) is an international research program studying social, political, economic, religious and cultural values of people around the world (2) and contributes to the monitoring of the Sustainable Development Goals (1). It utilises representative comparative social studies - conducted globally every five years - as its main research instrument (2). The WVS grew out of the [European Values Study](#) and was started in 1981 by Professor Ronald Inglehart from the University of Michigan and his team. It currently covers the time period from 1981 to 2022 (3) in more than 120 world societies (2) via 7 separate survey waves (3). Future iterations of the survey are to be added in the future, such as wave 8 of the survey which will cover the time frame from 2024-2026 (1). The goal of the Survey is to “assess which impact values stability or change over time has on the social, political and economic development of countries and societies” (2).

Every country included within the WVS is surveyed once every 5 years while employing random representative samples of the adult population. The majority of surveys were conducted using face-to-face interviews (both PAPI [paper questionnaires] and CAPI [Computer Assisted Personal Interviews]) as the data collection mode. Other methods can only be employed under specific circumstances after an application to the WVSA Scientific Committee. The sample should cover at least 95% of the total population of a given Country. Depending on the countries size, sample sizes are divided into three groups: (a) the standard group - which most countries belong to - where the sample should include 1.200 completed interviews, (b) countries with a population of less than two million, in which case 1.000 completed interviews suffice, and (c) countries with bigger population and greater population distribution which should aim for 1.500 completed interviews. Unless the country's territory is particularly big or the planned sample size exceeds 3000 respondents, the data collection should be completed within a time span of four weeks (5).

During the sampling process the following factors also needed to be considered:

- No region should deliberately be excluded from the survey unless it is a remote location inhabited by 1-3% of the population (excluding regions under an ongoing military conflict where the safety of interviewers and respondents cannot be guaranteed)
- In exceptional cases (e.g. voting rights granted earlier or a large share of young population) population in the age of 16+ can be interviewed, otherwise samples should cover the adult population in the age of 18+.
- Unless the share of migrants exceeds 50%, the WVS sample should also cover residents and not only citizens. The “residents” category does not include tourists or temporary visitors. Migrant workers however, can be surveyed in the case that they have spent at least 24 months in the given country prior to the survey date.

The ultimate goal is to cover all population groups who comprise the structure of a country's society at present. To achieve this, the latest census or official statistical data (if the census is outdated) is used to produce sample calculations (5).

The core variables considered in the surveys consist of:

- Social Values, Norms, Stereotypes
- Happiness and Wellbeing,
- Social Capital, Trust and Organizational Membership
- Economic Values,
- Perceptions of Corruption
- Perceptions of Migration
- Perceptions of Security
- Index of Postmaterialism
- Perceptions about Science and Technology
- Religious Values
- Ethical Values
- Political Interest and Political Participation
- Political Culture and Political Regimes (5)

The WVS is one of the most authoritative and widely-used cross-national surveys in the social sciences. It is the largest non-commercial cross-national empirical time-series investigation of human beliefs and values, standing out because of its extensive geographical and thematic scope, and the fact that it includes both very poor and very rich societies in all the world's main cultural zones (2). The data is frequently used by governments, scholars, students, journalists and international organizations to analyse topics such as economic development, democratization, religion, gender equality, social capital, and subjective well-being (2).

The documentation of the data is available for download as data files and pdf documents including results, the complete questionnaires (in both English as well as the native language and providing frequency distribution) and the technical/methodological description (4). The data is available on three levels: country documentation, wave documentation, and longitudinal documentation (3). The results from the different waves can alternatively also be analysed online using a simple interface (currently available at <https://www.worldvaluessurvey.org/WVSONline.jsp>). This interface also offers a cartographical and temporal overview of the data as well as a "compare" feature (4). In the section "Data and Documentation / Data Download" the questionnaire and a documentation are available for direct download. The documentation includes the codebook and descriptive statistics of the results for all countries. The documentation for the 7th wave of the survey has a total length of 1380 pages. The "statistical data files" containing the original raw data in different formats (csv, R, SAS, SPSS and STATA) are available for download immediately after

submission of the online registration form. According to the information provided on the website (as of 16 October 2024), the data files are available without restrictions, provided a) that they are used for non-profit purposes; b) correct citations are provided and sent to the World Values Survey Association for each publication of results based in part or entirely on these data files; c) the data files themselves are not redistributed; d) proper citation to the WVS data is included into the references list of the publication (citation format available for downloading in the Documentation section) (9).

Discuss Data relevant country coverage:

Country	Year	Sample Size	Languages Fielded	Institute conducting the Survey
Armenia	1997, 2011, 2021	2000, 1100, 1.223	Armenian, Russian	(1) Sociological Research Center (Armenian Academy of Sciences), Yerevan (Armenia); (2) CRRC, Armenia; (3) Caucasus Research Resource Center-Armenia Foundation
Belarus	1990, 1996, 2011	1015, 2092, 1535	Russian	(1) Institut of Sociology, Belarus Academy of Sciences (Minsk); (2) NOVAK-Laboratory, Institute (Minsk) (3) Serban Tanasa
Estonia	1996, 2011	1021, 1533	Estonian, Russian	(1) Center for Social Studies in Eastern Europe (Tallinn); (2) Saar Poll LLC
Georgia	1996, 2009, 2014	2008, 1500, 1202	Georgian	(1) Georgian Institute of Public Opinion (GIPO), Tbilisi; (2&3) GORBI
Kazakhstan	2011, 2018	1500, 1.276	Kazakh, Russian	(1) TOO «BISAM CENTRAL ASIA» for and under control BASHKIROVA AND PARTNERs, Ltd; (2) Public Opinion Research Institute

Kyrgyzstan	2003, 2011, 2020	1.043, 1500, 1.200	Kirghiz, Russian	(1) East-West Center for Research, American University; (2) Центр Изучения Общественного мнения и Прогнозирования «Эл- Пикир»; (3) Central Asia Barometer
Latvia	1996	1200	Latvian, Russian	Foundation for the Advancement of Sociological Studies, Riga
Lithuania	1997	1009	Lithuanian, Russian	-Baltic Surveys (Vilnius)
Moldova	1996, 2002, 2006	984, 1008, 1046	Moldavian, Russian	(1&2) Institute of Sociology, Moldovan Academy of Sciences (Chisinau); (3) Independent Sociological and Information Service “ OPINIA”
Russia	1990, 1995, 2011, 2017	1961, 2040, 2500, 1.810	Russian	(1) Institute for Social and Political Research, Soviet Academy of Science (Moscow); (2) Russian Public Opinion and Market Research [ROMIR] (Moscow); (3) Levada Analytical Center; (4) Higher School of Economics
Tajikistan	2020	1.200	Tajik, Russian	Research Centre SHARQ /Oriens
Ukraine	1996, 2006, 2011, 2020	2811, 1000, 1500, 1.289	Ukrainian, Russian	(1) Social Monitoring Center, National Institute for Strategic Studies (Kiev); (2) ROMIR Monitoring; (3) Research & Branding Group;

				(4) SO “Institute for Economics and Forecasting, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine”
Uzbekistan	2011, 2022	1500, 1.250	Uzbek	(1) “Ekspert fikri” Centre for Social and Marketing Research www.expert-center.uz (2) No information provided

Sources:

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